

REGMAR (MarineTime Regulation): LLM-Based RAG & Multi-Agent AI for Maritime Cybersecurity

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Abstract—The maritime industry is undergoing rapid digital transformation, driven by Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) as regulated by the International Maritime Organisation (IMO). This transformation has introduced unprecedented cybersecurity challenges. To address these issues, the IMO and the International Association of Classification Societies (IACS) have introduced various cybersecurity regulations, which are interpreted and implemented through diverse approaches by individual classification societies. However, the maritime sector continues to face significant challenges in the application and interpretation of these regulations. This study proposes a multi-agent and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) based framework, designed for integration with generative AI models, to enable the effective application of cybersecurity regulations issued by various classification societies using diverse large language models (LLMs). The practicality and applicability of the proposed framework have been demonstrated, highlighting its potential to mitigate the difficulties faced by the maritime industry in complying with cybersecurity regulations. Furthermore, this research contributes to the accelerated adoption of robust cybersecurity measures across the maritime sector.

Index Terms—Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS), Multi-Agent Systems, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), Large Language Models (LLMs), AI-based Regulation Compliance, Digital Transformation

I. INTRODUCTION

The IMO has defined levels of autonomy for ships and actively promoted the digitisation of the maritime sector under the Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) concept. In response to [1], the IACS published documents E26 and E27 [2] in 2022, emphasising the necessity of cybersecurity for ships and providing relevant guidelines. These documents were subsequently revised in September 2023 (E27) and November 2023 (E26), with an effective application date of 1 July 2024.

Following the publication of the IACS E26 and E27 guidelines, individual classification societies have developed and implemented their own cybersecurity regulations based on these standards. Ships possess unique characteristics—including large scale, operation in harsh marine environments, and complex navigation systems—that distinguish them from vehicles and aircraft.

Due to significant technological advancements—such as the adoption of autonomous ships and Digital Twin (DT) technolo-

gies—vessels have become increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats [3]–[7]. The inherent complexity of understanding and implementing cybersecurity principles across the maritime industry represents one of the most significant challenges in enforcing regulations. For example, based on industry feedback, the IACS extended the implementation deadline for Unified Requirements UR E26 and UR E27—from the originally scheduled 1 January 2024, to July 1, 2024—thereby postponing their introduction by six months [8]. This extension was intended to provide stakeholders with additional time to adapt to the new requirements, enhance their understanding of cybersecurity measures, and address integration challenges while managing the financial burden of compliance. Equipment manufacturers, shipyards, and shipowners have encountered considerable difficulties in interpreting cybersecurity requirements and integrating them into existing vessel systems. High costs, the absence of standardised technologies, and the complexity of system integration further exacerbate these challenges [9], [10].

This study aims to address these issues by resolving three major challenges associated with the implementation of ship cybersecurity regulations.

- 1) To provide a clear understanding of cybersecurity principles and relevant regulations through the utilisation of an LLM (REGMAR)¹ capable of addressing maritime cybersecurity.
- 2) To accelerate the adoption of ship cybersecurity regulations by employing an AI (REGMAR) specifically designed for maritime cybersecurity.
- 3) To mitigate the risk of information leakage inherent in the use of LLMs and to promote the integration of AI technologies by leveraging a local LLM.

By tackling these issues, this research seeks to contribute to the swift and precise adoption of ship cybersecurity regulations and, ultimately, to the establishment of a safer maritime environment.

¹REGMAR is the framework proposed in this study, and its name is a portmanteau of "regulation" and "MarineTime."

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Multi-Agent Research

The study titled *Mixture-of-Agents Enhances Large Language Model Capabilities* [11] introduces an innovative approach that leverages a division of roles between proposers and aggregators to generate responses from diverse perspectives and integrate them into high-quality outputs. This research achieves high performance without modifying the internal structure of the model, relying solely on prompt-based interfaces. Additionally, it surpasses existing state-of-the-art models, including GPT-4, and demonstrates outstanding performance on major benchmarks such as AlpacaEval 2.0, MT-Bench, and FLASK. However, the Mixture-of-Agents approach faces limitations, such as delays in Time to First Token (TTFT), highlighting the need for systematic architectural optimisation in future research.

B. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Research

a) *HippoRAG: Neurobiologically Inspired Long-Term Memory for Large Language Models:* [12] Introduces a framework that mimics human long-term memory by integrating knowledge graphs with active retrieval mechanisms. It outperforms traditional RAG approaches on multiple benchmarks. However, it incurs high computational and time costs for graph construction and maintenance, faces scalability challenges with large datasets, and may degrade in performance when domain-specific knowledge is limited.

b) *Development and Testing of Retrieval-Augmented Generation in Large Language Models:* [13], [14] Evaluates RAG in the healthcare domain by integrating structured clinical guidelines using tools such as LangChain and Elasticsearch. The method reduces hallucinations and produces more reliable responses. Limitations include strong dependence on data and guideline quality, additional computational overhead during retrieval that hinders real-time response, and reduced efficiency when handling queries involving unstructured information.

C. Research Gap in the Literature Review

Researchers have leveraged multi-agent systems and RAG to overcome the limitations of LLMs in healthcare, law, and education [15]–[18]. However, these studies have focused on domains with high data accessibility, leaving specialized industries like maritime cybersecurity under-researched [19].

This study proposes a framework combining multi-agent systems, RAG architectures, and localized LLMs to integrate and analyze maritime cybersecurity regulatory data. As digitalized vessel systems face increasing cyber threats while international regulations remain inadequate [20]–[23], our approach aims to enhance accuracy and reliability by optimizing LLM collaboration and incorporating maritime-specific regulatory and security information via RAG.

1) Domain-Specific Integration of RAG Architectures:

This study utilises RAG to effectively integrate unstructured maritime data and regulatory requirements,

ensuring both reliability and accuracy in the generation and application of dynamic cybersecurity solutions.

2) Collaborative LLM Framework via Multi-Agent Systems:

The framework employs multi-agent systems, enabling multiple LLMs to collaborate in addressing complex maritime cybersecurity scenarios. Each agent specialises in specific tasks, such as regulatory analysis or data verification, to maximise efficiency and performance.

This study proposes a practical framework for maritime cybersecurity regulation comprehension using generative AI and multi-agent systems, enhancing digitalization and safety while opening the door to applications in other specialized fields, thereby contributing to cybersecurity research.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study proposes a comprehensive methodology, REF-MAR, designed to analyse maritime cybersecurity regulatory documents. The methodology is structured into three primary phases: Common Steps, Agent Configuration Steps, and Multi-Agent Configuration.

A. Common Steps

The initial phase involves the collection and analysis of maritime cybersecurity regulatory documents. In this phase, relevant documents are gathered from various sources and subsequently classified to verify whether they pertain to ship cybersecurity regulations. Key regulatory requirements are then extracted through a detailed analysis, and the core concepts and keywords in each document are identified. Following this, the connections and relationships between documents are analysed manually. Additionally, OCR and text analysis techniques are applied to process the documents, and finally, the necessary layers of agents for document processing are established.

B. Agent Configuration Steps

The second phase involves the Configuration of three specialised agents to manage data generation and processing:

- **Agent 1:** Assesses the complexity of the user query through vector-based similarity evaluation and regular expression-based keyword verification. In this process, SentenceTransformer [24] is utilised to vectorise the query. If the query is deemed simple, it is immediately routed to Agent 3; if it is considered complex, it is forwarded to Agent 2 for further analysis.
- **Agent 2:** Retrieves document metadata from a database and applies techniques such as hierarchical graph analysis to identify the relationships among regulatory documents. The analysis results are then structured in a format such as JSON and passed on to Agent 3.
- **Agent 3:** Vectorises the user query to retrieve relevant documents and integrates the relationship analysis provided by Agent 2 to generate the final response. Finally, the DeepSeek-R1 14B [25] API is employed to produce a refined, context-aware response that reflects the inter-document relationships.

B. Agent Configuration Steps

This framework is composed of three agents—responsible, respectively, for interpreting the user query, analyzing document relationships, and generating the final response—and each agent performs the following detailed roles:

- **Agent 1:** Initially, the user query is vectorised using a SentenceTransformer. Similarity measures then applied to detect the presence of comparison-related keywords (e.g., "compare," "difference," "similarity"). If the similarity score between the query and the retrieved documents exceeds a predefined threshold and no comparison-related keywords are found, the system opts for a simple analysis pathway and directly invokes Agent 3. Otherwise, if the similarity is low or such keywords are present, the system deems a more detailed document relationship analysis necessary and calls Agent 2.
- **Agent 2:** This agent extracts document metadata (including titles, summaries, key keywords, and references) and inter-document linkage information from a PostgreSQL [28] database. Subsequently, it selects the top two to three maritime cybersecurity-related keywords from a JSON file to augment the search results. Using NetworkX [29], Agent 2 constructs a hierarchical graph of document relationships to determine the relative significance of each document (e.g., whether it represents a higher-level regulation or a more specific guideline). The resulting analysis is then converted into JSON format and forwarded to Agent 3.
- **Agent 3:** Agent 3 re-embeds the query and performs a FAISS-based [30] search to extract the top five relevant documents. It then processes the JSON output from Agent 2 to extract key keywords and identify documents particularly pertinent to specific classification society regulations. Finally, the content of these documents is integrated into a prompt, and the DeepSeek API is invoked to generate a refined response using an LLM model. This integrated approach ensures that the final answer incorporates both the direct FAISS search outcomes and the deeper document relationship analysis, thereby providing a highly reliable and comprehensive response. The following code snippet 1 exemplifies the agent routing logic implemented in this study.

```

1 def dispatch_question(query):
2     routing_decision =
3         determine_routing(query)
4         # Determine processing route
5     if routing_decision == "complex":
6         agent2_data = agent2_process(query)
7         if agent2_data:
8             final_answer = agent3_process(
9                 query, agent2_data
10            )
11        else:
12            final_answer =
13                agent3_process_simple(query)
14    else:

```

```

13         final_answer =
14             agent3_process_simple(query)
15     return final_answer
# Return AI-generated response

```

Listing 1. Agent Routing Logic

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Results

1) *quantitative evaluation:* Quantitative evaluation measures how closely the LLM's responses align with 100 best practices in maritime cybersecurity. Table I compares the performance of DeepSeek-R1 14B, REGMAR, and Llama3.2-Version 11B using BLEU, ROUGE-1, and ROUGE-L metrics. For BLEU, Llama3.2 achieves a mean score of 0.0108 (min 0.0000, max 0.0809), which is lower than DeepSeek-R1 14B (mean 0.032, max 0.111) and markedly lower than REGMAR (mean 0.158, max 0.302). In ROUGE-1, Llama3.2 records a mean score of 0.3350 (min 0.0608, max 0.5643), a performance comparable to or slightly below DeepSeek-R1 14B (mean 0.358, max 0.605) but significantly inferior to REGMAR (mean 0.545, max 0.646). For ROUGE-L, Llama3.2's mean score is 0.1448 (min 0.0394, max 0.2111), similar to DeepSeek-R1 14B (mean 0.142, max 0.219) yet lower than REGMAR (mean 0.332, max 0.525).

Overall, Llama3.2 underperformed compared to REGMAR and DeepSeek-R1; notably, REGMAR achieved roughly five times higher BLEU scores and significantly better ROUGE-1 and ROUGE-L results, demonstrating the superiority of the RAG approach that integrates document relationship analysis and contextual information.

2) *qualitative evaluation:* Qualitative evaluation was conducted as follows. To assess the efficacy of the proposed REGMAR model, responses generated by both DeepSeek and REGMAR for an identical query related to maritime cybersecurity were compared. As illustrated in Figure 3, the DeepSeek model's response merely lists generic cybersecurity recommendations and fails to address the specific regulations and nuances pertinent to the maritime domain. In contrast, Figure 4 demonstrates that the REGMAR response provides detailed guidelines and regulations tailored specifically for maritime cybersecurity, thereby offering more precise and domain-relevant security recommendations. These findings substantiate that the proposed REGMAR model delivers more specialised and effective responses to maritime cybersecurity challenges.

3) *Discussion:* In this study, we evaluated the response quality of both the DeepSeek and the proposed REGMAR systems using quantitative and qualitative assessments to verify the effectiveness of our domain-specific approach for maritime cybersecurity. The quantitative evaluation presented in Table I employed BLEU, ROUGE-1, and ROUGE-L metrics, revealing that the RAG system consistently outperformed DeepSeek across all measures. From a qualitative perspective, we compared the responses generated by both systems for an identical maritime cybersecurity query. As illustrated in Figure 3,

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF DEEPSEEK, REGMAR, AND LLAMA

Metric	DeepSeek-R1 14B			REGMAR			Llama3.2-Version 11B		
	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max
BLEU	0.032	0.0000	0.111	0.158	0.053	0.302	0.0108	0.0000	0.0809
ROUGE-1	0.358	0.0355	0.605	0.545	0.302	0.646	0.3350	0.0608	0.5643
ROUGE-L	0.142	0.0267	0.219	0.332	0.199	0.525	0.1448	0.0394	0.2111

Fig. 3. Sample Response Generated by the DEEPSEEK

Fig. 4. Sample Response Generated by the REGMAR Framework

DeepSeek’s response consists solely of generic cybersecurity recommendations, failing to address the specialised regulations and nuances of the maritime domain. In contrast, as shown in Figure 4, the REGMAR response provides detailed guidelines and regulations specifically tailored to maritime cybersecurity, effectively reflecting the domain’s unique requirements. These results indicate that the RAG approach is highly effective at integrating relevant contextual information from the knowledge base, thereby generating responses that align closely with best practices in maritime cybersecurity. Consequently, the proposed REGMAR model contributes significantly to

the development of more professional and precise security measures in this domain.

B. Limitations

Table I demonstrates that the RAG system outperforms the baseline LLM model according to the BLEU, ROUGE-1, and ROUGE-L metrics; however, this study is subject to several limitations.

- 1) **Limitations of Evaluation Metrics:** BLEU and ROUGE only measure n-gram overlap and may miss semantic or contextual correctness.
- 2) **Low Absolute Scores:** Varied expression styles yield low BLEU/ROUGE values that do not necessarily reflect actual response quality.
- 3) **Dataset Limitations:** Evaluation on 40 regulatory documents and 100 Q&A samples may not generalize to other maritime or safety datasets.
- 4) **Constraints of the Evaluation Methodology:** Reliance on quantitative metrics excludes semantic-based measures, real-time performance, and human judgments.

In summary, although the present study quantitatively demonstrates the superiority of the RAG system, the aforementioned limitations indicate that further follow-up research is required. Consequently, the research team plans to address these shortcomings in subsequent studies.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)-based multi-agent system for analyzing and applying maritime cybersecurity regulations. The framework comprises three specialized agents:

- 1) **Agent 1:** FAQ-based query analysis.
- 2) **Agent 2:** Hierarchical document-relationship analysis.
- 3) **Agent 3:** FAISS-based vector search combined with LLM-driven response generation.

By dynamically selecting the optimal analytical path for each user query, our system achieves enhanced precision and contextual relevance.

A. Key Findings

- **Improved Retrieval Accuracy:** Document-relationship analysis significantly outperforms standard vector-based retrieval in locating relevant regulations.
- **Adaptive Multi-Agent Workflow:** Automatic query classification and dynamic routing—augmented by relational-database analysis when needed—enhance both efficiency and robustness.

- **Enhanced Compliance Support:** Leveraging LLMs enables the generation of structured, context-aware responses that better support regulatory compliance.

B. Future Work

- **Broader Evaluation Metrics:** Incorporate semantic-based measures and human assessments to move beyond BLEU and ROUGE.
- **Larger, Diverse Datasets:** Validate generalizability by testing on expanded maritime datasets (e.g., safety and environmental regulations).
- **Operational Validation:** Develop real-world benchmarks to assess reliability, latency, and user experience in live maritime environments.
- **Integration with Cybersecurity Tools:** Explore interfacing with specialized security platforms and domain-specific protocols for practical compliance validation.

Our multi-agent RAG framework sets a new benchmark for intelligent regulatory analysis and lays the foundation for future advances in automated cybersecurity and compliance monitoring.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. M. Organization, "Maritime safety committee (msc), 100th session, 3–7 december 2018," <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/MeetingSummaries/Pages/MSC-100th-session.aspx>, 2018, accessed: February 17, 2025.
- [2] "Unified requirements – ur-e," accessed: February 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://iacs.org.uk/resolutions/unified-requirements/ur-e>
- [3] A. Turner, S. J. McCombie, and A. J. Uhlmann, "The impacts of cyber threat in the maritime ecosystem," p. 1378160, 2024.
- [4] M. Li, J. Zhou, S. Chattopadhyay, and M. Goh, "Maritime cybersecurity: A comprehensive review," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.11417*, 2024.
- [5] H. M. Tusher, Z. H. Munim, T. E. Notteboom, T.-E. Kim, and S. Nazir, "Cyber security risk assessment in autonomous shipping," *Maritime economics & logistics*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 208–227, 2022.
- [6] J. Yoo and Y. Jo, "Formulating cybersecurity requirements for autonomous ships using the square methodology," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 11, p. 5033, 2023.
- [7] Y. Jo, O. Choi, J. You, Y. Cha, and D. H. Lee, "Cyberattack models for ship equipment based on the mitre att&ck framework," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, p. 1860, 2022.
- [8] International Association of Classification Societies, "Iacs ur e26 and e27 press release," <https://iacs.org.uk/news/iacs-ur-e26-and-e27-press-release>, 2025, press release. Retrieved February 17, 2025.
- [9] S. Karamperidis, C. Kapalidis, and T. Watson, "Maritime cyber security: a global challenge tackled through distinct regional approaches," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 12, p. 1323, 2021.
- [10] A. J. Fenton, "Preventing catastrophic cyber–physical attacks on the global maritime transportation system: A case study of hybrid maritime security in the straits of malacca and singapore," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 510, 2024.
- [11] J. Wang, J. Wang, B. Athiwaratkun, C. Zhang, and J. Zou, "Mixture-of-agents enhances large language model capabilities," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.04692*, 2024.
- [12] B. J. Gutiérrez, Y. Shu, Y. Gu, M. Yasunaga, and Y. Su, "Hipporag: Neurobiologically inspired long-term memory for large language models," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.14831*, 2024.
- [13] Y. H. Ke, L. Jin, K. Elangovan, H. Abdullah, N. Liu, A. T. H. Sia, C. R. Soh, J. Y. M. Tung, J. C. L. Ong, and D. S. W. Ting, "Development and testing of retrieval augmented generation in large language models," Available at SSRN 4719185.
- [14] Y. Ke, L. Jin, K. Elangovan, H. R. Abdullah, N. Liu, A. T. H. Sia, C. R. Soh, J. Y. M. Tung, J. C. L. Ong, and D. S. W. Ting, "Development and testing of retrieval augmented generation in large language models—a case study report," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.01733*, 2024.
- [15] O. K. Gargari and G. Habibi, "An overview of medical knowledge evaluation of large language models: An endeavor toward a standardized evaluation and reporting guideline," 2025.
- [16] B. S. Posedaru, F.-V. Pantelimon, M.-N. Dulgheru, and T.-M. Georgescu, "Artificial intelligence text processing using retrieval-augmented generation: Applications in business and education fields," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, vol. 18, no. 1. Sciendo, 2024, pp. 209–222.
- [17] H. Jin, L. Huang, H. Cai, J. Yan, B. Li, and H. Chen, "From llms to llm-based agents for software engineering: A survey of current, challenges and future," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.02479*, 2024.
- [18] A. P. Smit, N. Grinsztajn, P. Duckworth, T. D. Barrett, and A. Pretorius, "Should we be going mad? a look at multi-agent debate strategies for llms," in *Forty-first International Conference on Machine Learning*.
- [19] T. Miller, I. Durlík, E. Kostecka, A. Łobodzińska, K. Łazuga, and P. Kozłowska, "Leveraging large language models for enhancing safety in maritime operations," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 3, p. 1666, 2025.
- [20] N. Ali, Y. Wang, and M. Chang, "Cybersecurity in the maritime domain: Challenges and regulatory gaps," *Marine Policy*, vol. 115, p. 103885, 2020.
- [21] M. A. Ben Farah, E. Ukwandu, H. Hindy, D. Brosset, M. Bures, I. Andonovic, and X. Bellekens, "Cyber security in the maritime industry: A systematic survey of recent advances and future trends," *Information*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 22, 2022.
- [22] S. Lee, Y. No, J. Cho, G. Jin, J. Kim, J. Lee, S. Jeon, F. A. Alfouzan, and K. Kim, "Securing maritime autonomous surface ships: Cyber threat scenarios and testbed validation," *IEEE Access*, 2025.
- [23] M. Caprolu, R. Di Pietro, S. Raponi, S. Sciancalepore, and P. Tedeschi, "Vessels cybersecurity: Issues, challenges, and the road ahead," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. —, 2020.
- [24] N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, "Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks," in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2019, pp. 3980–3990. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/D19-1410>
- [25] DeepSeek Team, "Deepseek-r1 14b," <https://www.deepseek.ai/>, 2023, deepSeek-R1 14B: A 14-billion parameter model for retrieval-augmented tasks.
- [26] LangGraph Team, "Langgraph framework," <https://www.langgraph.org/>, 2023, a framework for building composable applications with language models.
- [27] Ollama Team, "Ollama," <https://ollama.com>, 2023, accessed: February 17, 2025.
- [28] PostgreSQL Global Development Group, "Postgresql: The world's most advanced open source relational database," <https://www.postgresql.org/>, 2023, version 15.
- [29] A. A. Hagberg, D. A. Schult, and P. J. Swart, "Exploring network structure, dynamics, and function using networkx," in *Proceedings of the 7th Python in Science Conference (SciPy2008)*. Pasadena, CA, USA, 2008, pp. 11–15.
- [30] M. Douze, A. Guzhva, C. Deng, J. Johnson, G. Szilvasy, P.-E. Mazaré, M. Lomeli, L. Hosseini, and H. Jégou, "The faiss library," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.08281*, 2024.